

Studies on Pyrazoline. Part-II. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 3-(3'-Phenylsulphonamidophenyl)-5-aryl-1H/phenyl/acetyl pyrazolines

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In continuation of our work on pyrazoline derivatives¹, we have synthesised various pyrazolines (2). *m*-Aminoacetophenone was condensed with benzenesulphonyl chloride to get 3-(*N*-sulphonamidophenyl)acetophenone, which was then condensed with various aromatic aldehydes to get the chalcones (1). The chalcones on treatment with hydrazine hydrate/phenyl hydrazine/hydrazine hydrate and acetic acid gave substituted-pyrazolines (2).

The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method² at a concentration of 50 µg ml⁻¹ using Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus citreus*, Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and fungi *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus flavus*. It was observed that most of the compounds were found moderately active (14–27 mm zone of inhibition) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectrum (KBr) was taken on a Shimadzu IR-1435 spectrophotometer.

3'-Phenylsulphonamido chalcones (1) : Benzaldehyde (0.01 mol, 1.06 g) in ethanol (95%; 10 ml) was added to a mixture of 3-(*N*-sulphonamidophenyl)acetophenone (0.01 mol, 3.63 g) in ethanol (95%; 25 ml), aqueous NaOH (1%; 6 ml) and ethanol (95%; 10 ml) and stirred at 20–30° for 2–3 h. The contents were then kept for 24 h at 0–10°, filtered and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 160°; ν_{\max} (KBr) R = *p*-methoxyphenyl, 3 200 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 350 (S=O asym), 1 170 cm⁻¹ (S=O sym); *m/z* 378, 363, 316, 260, 252, 161, 156, 133, 107, 103. Similarly other chalcones were prepared, (yields 63–75%).

3-(3'-Phenylsulphonamidophenyl)-5-phenyl-1H/phenyl-pyrazoline (2) : A mixture of the chalcone (0.01 mol, 3.63 g) in ethanol (25 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol, 0.78 g)/phenyl hydrazine (0.01 mol, 1.08 g) and piperidine (2 ml) was refluxed for 8–10 h. The mixture was then concentrated, cooled and poured into acidified ice-water. The resulting solid crystallised from ethanol. when X = H (68%), m.p. 245°; ν_{\max} (KBr) R = *p*-methoxyphenyl, 3 350 (NH), 2 850 (CH₂ ring), 3 275 (pyrazoline ring NH), 1 320

(S=O sym), 1 155 cm⁻¹ (S=O asym); when X = phenyl, (65%), m.p. 75°; when R = *p*-methoxyphenyl, ν_{\max} 3 250 (NH), 2 850 (CH₂ ring), 1 500 (N-Ph), 1 330 (S=O sym), 1 155 cm⁻¹ (S=O asym); *m/z* 392, 376, 363, 349, 337, 327, 300, 260, 251, 175, 134. Similarly compounds having X = COCH₃, were prepared using a mixture of the chalcone (0.01 mol, 3.6 g) in ethanol (25 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol, 0.50 g) and acetic acid (10 ml), (yields 65–74%)

TABLE I-M p DATA OF 3-(3'-PHENYLSULPHONAMIDOPHENYL)-5-ARYL-1H/PHENYL/ACETYL PYRAZOLINES

R	Compd 1 M p (°C)	Compd 2, M p (°C)		
		X = H	X = Ph	X = COCH ₃
Ph	160	245	75	105
<i>o</i> -Methoxy-Ph	115	165d	50	170
<i>m</i> -Methoxy-Ph	100	162	110	95
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-Ph	198	100	85	206
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-Ph	130	140	115	186
<i>m</i> -Hydroxy-Ph	125	109	75	175
<i>p</i> -Hydroxy-Ph	145	123	65	191
3,4-Dimethoxy-Ph	132	137	124	192
4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-Ph	141	135	82	174
<i>o</i> -Nitro-Ph	110	110	82	172
<i>m</i> -Nitro-Ph	200	85	105	145
<i>m</i> -Amino-Ph	141	139	105	199
<i>p</i> -Amino-Ph	135	131	73	209
<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-Ph	128	125	75	93
<i>o</i> -Chloro-Ph	115	145	65	140
<i>m</i> -Chloro-Ph	183	130	112	138
<i>p</i> -Chloro-Ph	120	118	55	103
3,4-Dichloro-Ph	122	110	90	145

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis

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References

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